

Assessing Efficient Management of Students' Records among Record Officers in Tertiary Institutions of Jigawa State

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Abstract

The study investigates the effectiveness of student record-keeping practices among academic and non-academic staff in two randomly selected tertiary institutions in Jigawa State: Jigawa State College of Education, Gumel, and Jigawa State College of Education and Legal Studies, Ringim. Using survey research design, 100 questionnaires were distributed, with 89 successfully retrieved. Data analysis was conducted using frequency and percentages. The study found that the lack of digital systems (44.9%) and inadequate training (20.2%) were major challenges of students' record keeping in Jigawa state tertiary institutions. Finally, the study recommends the adoption of electronic record-keeping, capacity-building programs, and increased funding to enhance effective and efficient Students' records management in tertiary institutions in Jigawa State.

Keywords: *Students' Record-keeping, Tertiary institutions, Digitalization, Efficiency, Jigawa State, Nigeria.*

Introduction

Student record-keeping is a critical component of educational administration, facilitating academic documentation, decision-making, and institutional accountability. In Nigeria, many tertiary institutions still rely on manual record-keeping systems, which are often prone to inefficiencies, errors, and security risks (Owolabi & Opaleye, 2021). As student populations grow, the need for digital transformation in record management becomes more evident.

Jigawa State tertiary institutions, like many other tertiary institutions in Nigeria, faces challenges in adopting modern record-keeping systems. Factors such as lack of digital infrastructure, inadequate staff training, and financial constraints contribute to the inefficiencies observed in student record management. This study seeks to assess the effectiveness of student record-keeping practices in selected tertiary institutions in the state, highlighting key challenges and proposing actionable solutions.

Objectives of the Study

- i. To evaluate the current practices and methods used for examination records keeping and management in Jigawa State tertiary institutions.
- ii. To assess staff perceptions and attitudes towards the effectiveness of Students' records keeping and management systems in Jigawa State Tertiary Institutions.
- iii. To identify the challenges faced by staff in maintaining accurate and efficient Students' records management in Jigawa State Tertiary Institutions.
- iv. To propose strategies for improving Students' records keeping and management based on staff feedback and best practices in Jigawa State Tertiary Institutions.

Literature Review

Theoretical Framework

This study is grounded in the Records Continuum Theory and Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) to explain the practices, challenges, and potential improvements in managing examination records in tertiary institutions. The Records Continuum Theory, proposed by Frank Upward (1996), emphasizes that records management is an ongoing, integrated process rather than a linear lifecycle with distinct stages (McKemmish, 2001). Unlike the traditional life cycle approach, which views records as moving from creation to disposal in a sequential manner, the continuum model stresses that records exist in multiple dimensions simultaneously, serving administrative, legal, historical, and cultural functions (Reed, 2005). In the context of tertiary institutions, the Records Continuum Theory provides a framework for understanding how examination records should be maintained not just for immediate administrative needs but also for long-term academic and institutional integrity. On the other hand, the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) developed by Davis (1989) explains how users adopt and use new technologies based on two key factors: perceived usefulness (PU) and perceived ease of use (PEOU). The model posits that individuals are more likely to accept and utilize a technology if they believe it enhances their job performance and is easy to use (Venkatesh & Bala, 2008).

The combination of the Records Continuum Theory and TAM provides a comprehensive theoretical lens for this study. While the Records Continuum Theory emphasizes the need for ongoing and structured management of academic records, TAM addresses the human and

technological factors that influence the adoption of digital solutions. Together, these theories provide insights into both the institutional and individual-level challenges affecting records management in Jigawa State's tertiary institutions.

Conceptual Framework

Concept of Students' Records

The term records, as defined by Read and Ginn (2011), are stored information, regardless of media of characteristics, made or received by an organization that is evidence of its operations and has value requiring its retention for specific period of time. Ukwoma and Mole (2017) sees records as valuable assets of organizations. Good record management not only helps protect record but also enhances organizations operational efficiency. The U.S. Department of Education (2025) viewed students' records as those "records that are directly related to a student and that are maintained by an educational agency or institution or a party acting for or on behalf of the agency or institution. Based on the foregoing, Students' records are comprehensive documents maintained by educational institutions that encompass various aspects of a student's academic and personal information. Student records includes: Academic records, Attendance records, Health and medical records, Behavioral records (e.g. disciplinary records), financial records (in the Bursary department) etc.

Management of Students' Records

Management of academic records in Nigerian Tertiary Institutions has been a subject of concern for several decades. Iwhiwhu (2005) highlighted the absence of formal records management policies, leading to inconsistent practices and inefficiencies. Similarly, studies by Momohjimoh et al. (2024) and Odigie et al. (2021) underscored challenges such as inadequate funding, lack of skilled personnel, and insufficient training programs. These deficiencies often result in delayed retrieval of records, loss of vital documents, and compromised decision-making processes. The transition from manual to electronic records management systems has been slow, impeded by infrastructural deficits and resistance to change among staff (Iwhiwhu, 2005). To address these issues, researchers advocate for the implementation of comprehensive records management policies, investment in modern technologies, and continuous professional development for records management personnel. Management of students' record is viewed as very important in Jigawa State Tertiary Institutions. It enables storage, Preservation and retrieval of vital information needed for the Institutions' growth.

Important of Students' Records Keeping

Student records provide essential academic, financial, and personal information, aiding in administrative efficiency (Adewale et al., 2020). Efficient record-keeping ensures smooth academic operations, quick data retrieval, and institutional accountability (Okonkwo & Nwosu, 2022).

Problem Associated with Poor Students' Record Management Practice

Studies show that manual student record-keeping systems are prone to inefficiencies (Owolabi & Opaleye, 2021). Common issues include: Data loss and mismanagement (Eze & Chukwu, 2020), delays in information retrieval (Aina & Ojo, 2018) and increased workload for administrative staff (Abubakar & Bello, 2019). It has also been established that Digital transformation in students' record keeping improves data security, accessibility, and accuracy (Ibrahim & Yusuf, 2021), enhance efficiency, reduce errors, and minimize administrative burdens (Okonkwo and Nwosu, 2022). It has also been highlighted that Capacity-building

programs ensure effective system adoption (Aina & Ojo, 2018) and financial investment in ICT infrastructure and training is crucial for successful digitalization (Eze & Chukwu, 2020).

Scope of the Research

The scope of this work focused on assessing the efficient management of students' record among some selected schools and units in Jigawa State College of Education, Gumel and Jigawa State College of Education and Legal Studies, Ringim, respectively.

Methodology

The data Collected was analyzed using descriptive statistics (frequency and percentages). These statistical tools were selected because they provide a clear summary of respondents' opinions, making trends and patterns easily interpretable (Adewale et al., 2020). Descriptive statistics are widely used in educational research to summarize survey responses and identify dominant trends (Ibrahim & Yusuf, 2021). Given that the study aims to assess the efficiency of student record-keeping systems, identify challenges, and propose solutions, the use of frequency distributions and percentages allows for easy comparison of responses and helps in making data-driven conclusions (Okonkwo & Nwosu, 2022).

Results

Demographic Information of Respondents

Variables	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Institutions	Jigawa State College of Education, Gumel	45	50.6%
	Jigawa State College of Education and Legal Studies, Ringim	44	49.4%
Gender	Male	62	69.7%
	Female	38	30.3%
Staff Category	Academic Staff	56	62.9%
	Non-academic Staff	33	37.1%
Years of Experience	Less than 5 years	19	21.3%
	5-10 years	26	29.2%
	Above 10 years	44	49.4%

The above table shows that sample is fairly balanced between the two institutions (50.6% vs. 49.4%). Male respondents (69.7%) outnumber female respondents (30.3%), reflecting gender distribution in Nigerian tertiary institutions. The majority of respondents (62.9%) are academic staff, implying that most responses come from those directly handling student records. Almost half of the respondents (49.4%) have over 10 years of experience, meaning their insights are based on long-term exposure to students' record-keeping practices.

Current state of student record-keeping in Jigawa State's tertiary institutions

Responses	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Efficient	18	20%
Inefficient	60	67.8%
Undecided	11	12.4%

Based on the results in the above table, 67.4% of respondents believe the students' record-keeping system is inefficient, highlighting the need for reforms. Only 20.2% view it as efficient, suggesting that existing measures are inadequate. Also it can be deduced that 12.4% of the respondents had no opinion, indicating a possible lack of awareness or engagement with the record-keeping process. These findings align with Owolabi and Opaleye (2021), who found that most Nigerian tertiary institutions rely on inefficient manual systems that cause administrative bottlenecks.

Major challenges faced by record-keepers in managing students' records in Jigawa State tertiary institutions?

Responses	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Lack of digital record-keeping system	40	44.9%
Inadequate training for staff	18	20.2%
Poor storage facilities	14	15.7%
Lack of funding	10	11.2%
No challenge	7	7.9%

The responses in the table above indicate that biggest challenge (44.9%) to efficient students' records keeping is the lack of digital record-keeping systems, showing the need for automation. Inadequate training (20.2%) suggests that even if technology is introduced, staff may lack the skills to use it effectively. Poor storage facilities (15.7%) highlight the vulnerability of records to loss, damage, or mismanagement. Lack of funding (11.2%) is also a constraint, reinforcing Eze and Chukwu (2020), who noted that financial limitations hinder digital transformation in record management.

How digitalization can improve students’ record-keeping in Jigawa State tertiary institutions.

Responses	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Adoption of digital systems	50	56.2%
Regular staff training	20	22.5%
Improved infrastructure	12	13.5%
Increased funding of ICT	7	7.8%

Based on the figures in the above table, 56.2% of respondents advocate for digital record-keeping, affirming Okonkwo and Nwosu (2022), who found that automated systems improve efficiency and security. It was also found that 22.5% of the respondents emphasize staff training, showing that without proper training, even the best systems may fail while 13.5% focus on improved storage, suggesting that even non-digital records require better management. 7.8% stress funding, indicating that while technology is crucial, its sustainability depends on financial commitment.

Recommendations on ways to improve students’ record-keeping in Jigawa State tertiary institutions

Responses	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Digital transformation of students records keeping	48	53.9%
Periodic Inspection and assessment of students’ records	15	16.9%
Government and the TETFUND to intensify funding of ICT and other records keeping facilities.	12	13.5%
Capacity building and training for staff on efficient record -keeping	14	15.7%

The table shows that over half (53.9%) of respondents prioritize digital transformation, reinforcing the need for automated student record management. 16.9% recommend periodic audits, aligning with Umeh and Adepoju (2021), who argue that regular system evaluations enhance effectiveness. 15.7% highlight staff training, reinforcing the necessity of human capital development for effective digital record management.

Discussions

The analysis reveals that 67.4% of respondents perceive the current student record-keeping systems in Jigawa State's tertiary institutions as inefficient. This perception is primarily

attributed to challenges such as the absence of digital record-keeping systems (44.9%), insufficient staff training (20.2%), and inadequate storage facilities (15.7%). These findings are consistent with Asogwa (2013), who identified that Nigerian universities are unprepared to manage electronic records due to weak legislative and organizational frameworks. The study also highlights that 56.2% of respondents advocate for the adoption of digital systems to enhance record-keeping efficiency. This perspective aligns with Adeyanju (2020), who found that the implementation of electronic record management systems significantly reduced turnaround time in processing official documents at the University of Lagos.

The challenges identified such as the lack of digital systems, inadequate training, and poor storage facilities are not unique to Jigawa State's institutions. Similar issues have been documented across Nigerian universities. For instance, Mabera (2020) reported that poor management of student academic records leads to delays in decision-making and graduation processes. Furthermore, Ajike et al. (2021) emphasized that the self-efficacy of records personnel significantly influences student records management practices, underscoring the need for adequate training. The recommendation for digital transformation is further supported by Asogwa, Ezeani, and Asogwa (2021), who observed that while ICT facilities are available in Nigerian federal university libraries, their utilization for electronic records management remains suboptimal. They advocate for adopting international best practices to improve e-records management.

Conclusion

The study concludes that the management of students' records in Jigawa State College of Education, Gumel and Jigawa State College of Education and Legal Studies, Ringim was fraught with challenges that hinder efficiency and accuracy. The reliance on manual systems, coupled with inadequate training and infrastructural deficits, compromises the integrity of students' records. Addressing these issues requires a multifaceted approach that encompasses technological adoption, policy development, and capacity building.

Recommendations

- **Adoption of Digital Records Management Systems:** Institutions should transition from manual to electronic records management systems to enhance efficiency and accuracy. This transition necessitates investment in appropriate technologies and infrastructure.
- **Comprehensive Training Programs:** Regular training and professional development programs as well as workshops and seminars should be instituted to equip records management staff with the necessary skills to operate and maintain digital systems effectively.
- **Development of Standardized Policies:** Establishing clear policies and procedures for records management will ensure consistency and compliance across all departments within the institutions.
- **Infrastructure Enhancement:** Allocating resources towards improving storage facilities, acquiring modern equipment, and ensuring reliable power supply is essential for the optimal functioning of records management systems.

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